

Tuning mono-divalent cation water composition by the capacitive ion-exchange mechanism

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ABSTRACT

Soil salinization poses a significant challenge to agricultural activities. To address this, the agricultural industry seeks an irrigation water solution that reduces both ionic conductivity and sodium adsorption rate (SAR), thereby diminishing the risks of soil sodification and fostering sustainable crop production. Capacitive deionization (CDI) is an attractive electrochemical technology to advance this search. Recently, a one-dimensional transient CDI model unveiled a capacitive ion-exchange mechanism presenting the potential to adjust the treated water composition by modifying monovalent and divalent cation concentrations, thereby influencing the SAR index. This behavior would be achieved by using electrodes rich in surface functional groups able to efficiently capture divalent cations during conditioning and releasing them during charging while capturing monovalent ions. Beyond the theoretical modelling, the current experimental research demonstrates, for the first time, the effectiveness of the capacitive ion-exchange mechanism in a CDI pilot plant using real water samples spiked with solutions containing specific mono and divalent ions. Electrosorption experiments and computational modeling, specifically Density-Functional Theory (DFT), were used along with the analysis of the surface functional groups present in the electrodes to describe the capacitive ion-exchange phenomenon and validate the steps involved on it, highlighting the conditioning as a critical step. Various operational and flow modes confirm the versatility of CDI technology, achieving separation factors ($R_{Mg/Na}$) of 5–6 in batch, raising production from 0.5 to 0.8 L m⁻² h⁻¹ (batch) to 8.0–8.1 L m⁻² h⁻¹ when using single pass although reducing $R_{Mg/Na}$ to 2. The reliability of the CDI technology in reducing SAR was also successfully tested with different influent compositions, including magnesium and calcium. Finally, the robustness of the capacitive ion-exchange mechanism was validated by a second CDI laboratory 9-cell stack cycled over 350 cycles. Our results confirm the reported theoretical model and expands the conclusions through the experiments in a pilot plant showing direct implications for employing CDI in agricultural applications.

1. Introduction

Competition for water resources is rising due to population growth and increased calorie consumption, requiring a 70 % increase in agricultural production by 2050 (Pardey et al., 2014). Irrigated agriculture, covering 20 % of cultivated land and contributing 40 % of global food production, is crucial for global food security, given its productivity compared to rainfed agriculture (Chi Zhang et al., 2018). Therefore, assessing water quality for irrigation is essential to meet growing crop

demand and maintain food and soil quality.

Soil degradation, primarily induced by soil salinization, is a critical threat to agricultural activities (Daliakopoulos et al., 2016). Soil salinization encompasses elevated salt concentrations (saline soils), high sodium levels (sodic soils), and increased pH (alkaline soils) (Daliakopoulos et al., 2016). Elevated soluble sodium levels in sodic soils significantly impact soil physical properties by promoting colloidal dispersion and reducing soil permeability (de Souza Oliveira Filho et al., 2020). As exchangeable sodium hydrolyzes, interparticle bonds weaken,

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leading to swelling and detachment, and increasing dispersibility, making the soil more vulnerable to erosion by water and wind (De La Paix et al., 2013). Conversely, high concentrations of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Al^{3+} enhance soil aggregation. Soil degradation can result from natural processes (primary salinization) or human activities (secondary salinity). In the context of the latter, using low-quality water for irrigation, improper drainage practices, and excessive fertilizer application lead to salt accumulation (Haj-Amor et al., 2023). Salinization from irrigation practices affects over 20 % of the world's irrigated land, and some countries experience salt-affected soils on more than half of their irrigated acreage (Tomaz et al., 2020). For instance, the European Mediterranean region has 25 % of irrigated agricultural land facing moderate-to-high salinization, leading to moderate soil degradation (Daliakopoulos et al., 2016; Tomaz et al., 2020).

To evaluate the water quality for irrigation and its impact on the soils, key indicators such as electrical conductivity (EC), SAR, exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP), total dissolved solids (TDS) and pH, are employed to detect soil salinization (Daliakopoulos et al., 2016). For evaluating water suitability for agriculture, EC and SAR indices are traditionally employed in Riverside and Wilcox (% Na^+ instead of SAR) diagrams (Mostaza-Colado et al., 2018). EC quantifies the concentration of all soluble salts in water, while the SAR index considers the levels of alkaline cations (Na^+) and alkaline earth cations (primarily Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}), as outlined in Eq. (1).

$$\text{SAR} = \frac{C_{\text{Na}^+}}{\sqrt{C_{\text{Ca}^{2+}} + C_{\text{Mg}^{2+}}}} \quad (1)$$

where the concentrations (C) of Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} are expressed in mmol L^{-1} .

Hence, reducing Na^+ and Cl^- levels in irrigation water while maintaining those of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} is deemed a favorable goal. This approach aims to yield a water solution with lower conductivity and SAR values, thereby mitigating the risk of soil salinization. In light of this challenge, there is a growing interest in research focused on adjusting water composition regarding monovalent and divalent ion concentrations through electrochemical deionization technologies.

Current water treatment technologies used for selective sodium capture from a water matrix include membrane technologies, such as microfiltration (Al-Shammiri et al., 2005), nanofiltration (Chang et al., 2005) and reverse osmosis (Bunani et al., 2015). Nevertheless common drawbacks of reverse osmosis are associated to i) the complete removal of all ions, requiring a blending step water quality requirements (Bunani et al., 2015; Zarzo et al., 2013); and ii) the high pressures usually needed in this process, which increases the production costs (Bunani et al., 2015). Adsorption technologies with functionalized adsorbents and ion exchange resins offer a different approach (Qian and Schoenau, 2002; Wang et al., 2012). However, they require an additional step for either adsorbent or ion exchange resin regeneration, which involves chemical addition and yields a concentrated salt solution needing proper disposal (Qian and Schoenau, 2002). In contrast, electrochemical technologies might use "green" electrons (those produced by renewable energies) to enable selective or preferential separations through membranes, electrodes, or a combination of both (Alkhadra et al., 2022; Cohen et al., 2018; Mao et al., 2019).

Capacitive deionization (CDI) is an electrochemical water treatment method based on ion electrosorption, which has garnered attention from the scientific community over the past decade (Anderson et al., 2010; Porada et al., 2013; Suss et al., 2015; Suss and Presser, 2018). CDI technology involves applying a cell potential to a pair of carbon-based electrodes to reduce the ion concentration of the solution by adsorbing ions in the electrochemical double layer (EDL) of the porous electrodes (Anderson et al., 2010; Suss et al., 2015). In a subsequent step, ions are desorbed from the electrodes into the solution, forming a brine by short-circuiting or inverting the cell potential. The mechanism, based on supercapacitor technology, combines water treatment with energy

storage, enhancing the energy efficiency of the technology (Anderson et al., 2010; Santos et al., 2020). Moreover, this dual process of ion electrosorption and desorption offers the potential to selectively capture and recover specific ions by electrode functionalizing (Choi et al., 2019; Lado et al., 2017; Oliveira et al., 2023; Oyarzun et al., 2018). This ability to reclaim certain ions underscores the significance of CDI technology in promoting the circular economy, particularly within the water sector (Kumar et al., 2023). Additionally, CDI benefits from low voltages, reduced pressures, and moderate temperatures in operational conditions, along with the capacity to recover some of the energy used in the electrosorption step, resulting in low energy consumption (García-Quismondo et al., 2013b; Pernía et al., 2012; Santos et al., 2021). Moreover, the costs of the carbon materials used as active materials in the electrodes are relatively low and can be sourced from bio-waste materials (Lado et al., 2016, 2019; Sriramulu et al., 2019).

On the other hand, research has identified certain weaknesses in this technology (Changyong Zhang et al., 2018). The co-ion repulsion effect from the adsorption of ions of the same charge as the polarized electrode reduces charge efficiency, increasing energy consumption (Biesheuvel and van der Wal, 2010; Li and Zou, 2011). Proposed alternatives include ion exchange membranes and polymer coatings, which limit this effect but raise the cost of the electrochemical cell/stack (McNair et al., 2021; Perez-Antolin et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2022). Besides the co-ion effect, undesired faradaic reactions negatively affect to energy consumption, electrode stability and treated water composition leading to the production of by-products (Aytac et al., 2023; Cohen et al., 2013; He et al., 2016; Lado et al., 2014; Changyong Zhang et al., 2018). Among faradaic reactions, carbon electrode oxidation is the most significant due to its adverse impact on CDI performance and electrode lifespan, affecting structural (pore size distribution and mass loss) and electrochemical properties (electrode potential shifting and electric resistance) (Chen et al., 2013; Cohen et al., 2011, 2013; Gao et al., 2014; Kang et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2020). Additionally, it is worth noting that, although growing in recent years, there is a lack of studies focused on engineering aspects like electrical configuration or scaling up the CDI technology (Dinh et al., 2023; Shen et al., 2021; Tan et al., 2020). Finally, it should be remarked that most CDI research has used single electrolyte solutions, primarily NaCl, though this trend is shifting towards more complex studies involving water compositions beyond NaCl. All these factors have been identified as obstacles to the technology's further development (Lado et al., 2021b; Pang and Shen, 2022).

New horizons for CDI have emerged, moving beyond desalination to more applications like pollutants removal, critical materials capture, customizing water composition for purposes in, e.g. agri-food industry (Pang and Shen, 2022; Xing et al., 2020). Consequently, various research groups have explored the tunable ion selectivity in CDI by altering the surface chemistry and morphology of carbon electrodes through various treatments (Gamaethiralalage et al., 2021; Guyes et al., 2021; Uwayid et al., 2022; Yu et al., 2019). For structural modifications, Cerón et al. proposed enhancing selective adsorption by modifying the pore-size distribution within hierarchical carbon aerogel monoliths, targeting calcium or sodium ions (Cerón et al., 2020). Additionally, Avraham et al. used carbon chemical vapor deposition to tune the pore size, obtaining carbon molecular sieves for selective separation of sodium from divalent cations (Avraham et al., 2008). Regarding chemical surface functionalization, Guyes et al. demonstrated size-based ion selectivity when using an oxidized cathode, with smaller hydrated ions preferentially electrosorbed when an increased number of surface groups (e.g. carboxylic groups) were introduced into the micropores (Guyes et al., 2019). Further research in this group showed that functionalizing the cathode with sulfonic groups led to time-dependent selectivity (Guyes et al., 2021), shifting from a monovalent selectivity during short charging intervals to predominant divalent adsorption during longer durations. This aligns with previous work reported by Zhao et al. (Zhao et al., 2012b) and Choi et al. (Choi et al., 2016). Extreme monovalent ion selectivity was recently reported using a sulfonated

cathode and a pristine anode, demonstrating CDI cell behavior as a capacitive ion-exchange (CIE) system (Sahray et al., 2023). The authors also modeled a symmetric CDI cell equipped with sulfonated carbon electrodes, predicting that the functionalized anode can primarily electro-sorb divalent cations before the charging step begins. Due to the high electronic charge induced in the anode by the sulfonic groups, the model shows that CDI cell will release divalent cations during charging while removing sodium, acting as an ion-exchange resin without the need of regenerating chemicals.

In this study, we parallel the research conducted by the Suss group, expanding upon the theoretical model introduced by Sahray et al. (Sahray et al., 2023), validating it through experimentation with a CDI pilot plant. Our focus is on a CDI stack equipped with graphite felt (GF) electrodes modified with activated carbon containing oxygen groups, known from previous work (Freire et al., 2021; Lado et al., 2021a, 2021b; Wang et al., 2020), for reducing the SAR index through capacitive ion exchange mechanisms. Our research not only supports Sahray et al.'s model but also extends its conclusions to an industrial-scale CDI stack, treating real waters with varying sodium and magnesium concentrations. Moreover, using thicker GF electrodes (4.6 vs. 0.6 mm), we enhance capacitive ion exchange, resulting in increased water production with an appropriate mono/divalent ion ratio. Exploring different experimental conditions maximizes selectivity and stabilizes performance throughout the cycling process. Additionally, we will provide computational modeling analysis to assess the impact of various surface groups on the electrodes. Therefore, our proposal is to use an energy-efficient CDI treatment to reduce the SAR index and conductivity in irrigation systems, thereby mitigating the risk of soil sodification and ultimately enhancing crop production. This research is contextualized within the Water-Energy-Food Nexus, emphasizing the interdependence of water, energy, and food (Chi Zhang et al., 2018).

2. Experimental

2.1. CDI electrodes

A 10 cell-CDI stack was assembled using 20 GF-AC electrodes of 2400 cm² projected geometric area. Initially, GF materials (SGL, GFD4.6) were thermally activated at 200 °C for 4 h and impregnated with an activated carbon ink. The methodology to prepare that ink was described in a previous study in which a Vanadium Redox Flow Battery (VRFB) was reconfigured as a 5-cell CDI Stack equipped with 1250 cm² electrodes (Lado et al., 2021b). Briefly, polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF, Alfa Aesar) was dissolved in isopropanol using a paddle mixer, to subsequently add activated carbon (PICACTIF SuperCap BP10 type, from now referred as PICA) and carbon black (acetylene, Alfa Aesar) in a ratio 1:1:8 PVDF:PICA:Acetylene. Once GF were impregnated with the ink, the GF-AC was dried using a heat table at 120 °C for 2 h. The average AC mass loading of the electrodes employed in the CDI stack ranged 40 ± 5 mg cm⁻², giving an average of 96 g of activated carbon per electrode and 1920 g per 10-cell stack. Information about the physical and electrochemical characterization of GF-AC was previously reported by our group (Wang et al., 2020). Regarding the BET surface area, GF-AC reached 621 m² g⁻¹ as a result of the combination of the GF (4 m² g⁻¹) and the PICA carbon (2410 m² g⁻¹) with contribution of both micro and mesopores). Furthermore, a thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) coupled to a mass spectrometer found the presence of surface oxygen groups (SOGs) (Vaquero et al., 2012).

Additional characterizations of the activated carbon were performed in this study, including zeta potential analysis conducted on a Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Instruments). Furthermore, the nature of the surface functional groups present in the pristine electrode material was characterized by X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS). Spectra were recorded in a SPEC PHOIBOS NAP-150 1D equipment utilizing a monochromatic Al K α 1 radiation from a source operated at 50Watts and instrumental overall energy resolution of 0.5 eV for high-resolution

spectra. Finally, the potential of zero charge (E_{PZC}) of PICA carbon was determined by electrochemical measurements using an electrochemical workstation (Biologic VMP3 multichannel potentiostat-galvanostat coupled with EC-Lab v11.42 software). Drop casting electrode (carbon paper coated with the aforementioned ink, 0.785 cm², 0.336 mg) was submitted to cyclic voltammogram at 1 mV s⁻¹ between -0.4 V and 0.8 V using a three electrodes cell with Ag/AgCl as reference, platinum mesh as a counter electrode and 5 mM NaCl as electrolyte solution. E_{PZC} was estimated considering the electrode potentials (anodic and cathodic) in which the capacitance values were minimum (Gao et al., 2015). To evaluate the effect of the oxidation upon cycling on the positive electrode, a cycle galvanostatic charge-discharge experiment was performed over 100 cycles setting a 30 min constant voltage step. Potential window between 0.0 V and 1.0 V was established using 0.06 mA cm⁻² and 0.03 mA cm⁻² as charging and discharging current densities, respectively.

2.2. CDI stack

The CDI stack was composed by 10 cells in a filter press configuration including PVC end plates, aluminum end plate, copper current collector plates, bolts and compression springs as auxiliary components to achieve and adequate seal and compression fixture (Fig. 1a). Each cell was composed by the following elements: two GF-AC electrodes of 2400 cm², separated by a synthetic filter separator (PEX-77,300), a piece of expanded graphite bipolar current collectors (TF6, SGL, 0.6 mm) that allows the electrical connection of the cells in series, flow frame plates for negative and positive sides (low density polyethylene) previously optimized by a fluid-dynamic analysis developed with software package COMSOL Multiphysics (additional information and figures included in Sup. Info Figure S1 and Table S1), and gaskets employed to seal the compartments. The electrical connection to the power supply was made through copper terminals and final endplates (60 cm × 67 cm) were placed on the sides to facilitate the alignment of the different components and the application of certain pressure to close the stack (Fig. 1b).

2.3. CDI pilot plant

The CDI stack was integrated in a fully functional pilot plant as shown in Fig. 1c. The electrochemical performance of the stack was carried out by a galvanostatic charging and discharging equipment (constant current, CC mode) based on a power supply (Delta Elektronika, SM-70-AR-24) combined with an electronic load (Kikusui, PLZ-205 W). A LabVIEW software interface was used to set the current on the programmable charger and load, set the current intensity and set the voltage limits. Additionally, a potentiostatic step (constant voltage, CV) was included in the testing protocol with the aim of stabilizing the performance and based on previous studies (García-Quismondo et al., 2016). This system was configured in such a way that the energy demand of the CDI stack can be quantified during the whole deionization cycle.

Stack performance was measured using an in-house designed test system. A pumping system, integrated by a centrifugal pump (Bombas Torres, MP-6086.9) flow meters and 4 different electrovalves (two of 2-way and two 3-way), was used to perform the experiments using two different operational modes, *i.e.* batch and single pass. Batch experiments were performed by recirculating through the system a volume of 26.4 L of simulated brackish water. In the case of single-pass experiments, reservoirs tanks with a capacity of 220 L were located at the inlet and outlet. Electrovalves and auxiliary tanks facilitate the sampling of effluent.

A multiparametric multimeter system (MM41 Hach) equipped with conductivity and pH probes located in the inlet and outlet of the reactor was employed to measure the variation of these parameters. Software developed by IMDEA Energy using LabVIEW environment was employed to launch, control and monitor the experiments while

Fig. 1. A) Design and configuration of the different components of the CDI stack. B) Picture of the assembled CDI stack. C) Picture of CDI Pilot Plant, showing the different elements of the system including: 1) CDI Stack; 2) Power supply and electronic load; 3) Conductivity and pH sensors along with the electrovalves; 4) Pumping System; 5) Computer equipped with LabVIEW application to control and monitor the experiments.

recording all the different variables such as, voltage, current, flow, pH and conductivity.

2.4. CDI experiments

Electrosorption experiments were performed at room temperature pumping different aqueous solutions into the stack at a flow rate of 40 L h⁻¹ to provide a mean linear flow rate of ≈ 1 cm s⁻¹ through the interelectrode gap of the 3.5 mm. Different reagents such as NaCl (98 % purity, Sigma-Aldrich), MgCl₂·2H₂O (98 % purity, Alfa Aesar) and CaCl₂·2H₂O (99 % purity, Alfa Aesar) were used without further purification to prepare simulated brackish water with different concentrations of Na⁺, Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺. The electrosorption performance was evaluated using the parameters and equations collected in **Table 1** and **Table S2**, being all of them described in detailed in our previous studies (Hawks et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020). The evolution of the different ion concentrations (Na⁺, Mg²⁺, and Cl⁻) was monitored by taking

Table 1

List of parameters employed in the evaluation of the CDI performance. Parameters have been defined based on Hawks et al. (Hawks et al., 2019). Equations corresponding each one of the parameters are listed in **Table S2**.

Variables	Description	Unit
SAC	Salt adsorption capacity in terms of active mass	mg g ⁻¹
ASAR	Average salt removal rate in terms of active mass	mg g ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Δc	Concentration reduction after treatment	mM
E_M	Molar energy consumption	Wh mol ⁻¹
E_V	Volumetric energy consumption per cubic meter of diluent	Wh m ⁻³ kWh m ⁻³
P	Water production using projected area of the electrode	L m ⁻² h ⁻¹

samples and analyzing them by Ion Chromatography (IC). Samples were analyzed using a 930 Compact IC Flex chromatographer (column was a Metrosep A SUPP 5 column for anions and Metrosep C 6–250/4.0 for cations).

The separation factor has been calculated using $R_{Mg/Na}$. R was defined by Gamaethiralalage et al. as the ratio between the effluent concentration (R_i) by feed concentration (R_j) of each ion. Here $R_{Mg/Na}$ is calculated in Eq. (2) during the CDI experiment by comparing the evolution of the concentration of Na⁺ (R_{Na} , Eq. (3)) and Mg²⁺ (R_{Mg} , Equation 4) and the correlation between both.

$$R_{Mg/Na} = \frac{R_{Mg}}{R_{Na}} \quad (2)$$

$$R_{Na} = \frac{C_{Na}^t}{C_{Na}^0}; R_{Mg} = \frac{C_{Mg}^t}{C_{Mg}^0} \quad (3)$$

Being C_X^0 and C_X^t the initial and final concentration at time t , respectively.

2.5. Computational modelling (DFT)

Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations were performed in order to elucidate the electrode affinity towards the sodium and magnesium cations. The GF-AC is modelled as an ovalene molecule with the formula C32H14, which consists of ten peri-fused, six-membered rings. The surface oxygen groups are simulated by placing several functional groups, such as carboxylic acids, catechol, ethers, hydroxyl, aldehyde and ketone groups, either at the edge sites or at the ring. Ionizable groups, such as hydroxyl, catechol and carboxylic groups, have also been considered in their deprotonated forms. In all calculations, the cations are considered to be in their hydrated form having a coordination

number of 6 or 4 in the case of sodium. Several initial structures are prepared, where the graphene-oxide model contains a hydrated metal cation adsorbed at a surface oxygen group. Subsequently, the structures are verified to be minima after performing a frequency analysis, where no imaginary frequencies are computed. The energy optimizations are performed using the B3LYP (Becke, 1993; Lee et al., 1988) functional in combination with the 6-31+G(d,p) basis set (denoted as BS1). Final electronic energies are calculated using the B3LYP and M06-2X functional (Zhao and Truhlar, 2008) in combination with the 6-311++G(d,p) basis set for non-metals and the LANL2DZ for sodium and magnesium (denoted as BS2). All calculations (geometry optimizations, frequency calculations and final single point energies) are carried out in aqueous phase with the solvent treated by the implicit universal solvation model SMD (Marenich et al., 2009). Free energies are calculated assuming $T = 298.15$ K and $P = 1$ atm, based on the quantum mechanical harmonic-oscillator approximation from the vibrational partition functions. All calculations have been performed utilizing the Gaussian 16 package (Frisch et al., 2016).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Batch experiments

3.1.1. Ion removal by CDI constant current mode

The CDI system was tested by performing batch experiments using CC mode to treat simulated brackish water (conductivity = $1530 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$) which main component was NaCl (Na^+ 300 mg L^{-1} , Cl^- 357 mg L^{-1}). Additionally, a low concentration of magnesium was added ($\text{Mg}^{2+} \approx 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) in order to evaluate the behavior of mono and divalent cations.

The results displayed in fig. 2a and fig. 2b show a reduction of the

ionic conductivity of $314 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ (average value of three cycles recorded at the end of the charging step) as response of the electrode polarization and the subsequent adsorption of the ions in the EDL. Despite the high stack voltage (*i.e.* 1.6 V per cell assuming a homogenous distribution of the potential through all the cells) only a slight increase of pH from 5.2 to 5.8 was observed. The moderate increase of the pH could be attributed to a parasitic reaction involving the reduction of the dissolved oxygen leading to the production of hydrogen peroxide and the raise of the pH. As it described by He et al., at low voltages cathodic reduction of O_2 and H_2O_2 prevails in the faradaic processes resulting in proton consumption and a subsequent pH increase (He et al., 2016). However, at higher cell voltages, the initial pH rise is followed by a pH reduction due to additional anodic oxidation reactions that produce protons. Despite the high stack voltage applied in this experiment (16 V), it is known that due to electrical losses and uneven distribution of the CDI stack voltage across cells (in series connection), the "real" potential applied to each cell could be below 1.6 V.

Samples taken during the first cycle (fig. 2c) showed the removal of sodium and chloride ions (Na^+ from 300 mg L^{-1} to 147 mg L^{-1} and Cl^- from 357 mg L^{-1} to 235 mg L^{-1}) resulting in a SAC of $3.8 \text{ mg}_{\text{NaCl}} \text{ g}^{-1}$ and an ASAR_c of $0.025 \text{ mg}_{\text{NaCl}} \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. In contrast, Mg^{2+} concentration increased as soon as the stack was polarized, growing consistently from 7 mg L^{-1} to 24 mg L^{-1} . Once this level was reached at approximately 14 V (after 100 min of the beginning of the polarization), the concentration of Mg^{2+} suffered a reduction, decreasing to 14 mg L^{-1} at the end of the charging step. These results are coherent with the conclusions of the model introduced by Sahray et al., in which an extreme monovalent ion selectivity is predicted when chemically functionalized electrodes are employed (Sahray et al., 2023). The high selectivity predicted by the model is the result of an increase in the concentration of divalent cations alongside with a decrease in monovalent cations. Nevertheless, a

Fig. 2. Results from electrosorption experiment performed in a CC mode at 6.3 A m^{-2} (charge) / -4.2 A m^{-2} (discharge) at max. stack voltage 16 V. A) Stack voltage and current profiles; B) Conductivity and pH profiles. Evolution of ion concentrations during the first (C) and eighth (D) cycle.

notable disparity emerges here: the chloride effluent concentration decreases, in contrast to the model's prediction of no substantial reduction. This discrepancy may be attributed to the fact that the model developed by Sahray et al. suggests that ion exchange occurs when the potential of zero charge of both the anode and the cathode remains positive throughout the entire potential window established during the charging step. Additionally, as acknowledged by the authors of the model, the potential of zero charge is influenced by the feed concentration. Consequently, both the degree of functionalization and the feed concentration impact the potential of zero charge of the electrodes, ultimately affecting the anode's ability to capture anions during the charging process. This discrepancy holds significance as it enables a reduction in water conductivity, consequently influencing the SAR index and, in turn, the suitability of the water for irrigation.

With the aim of following the evolution of the magnesium concentration upon cycling, the results obtained in the first cycle were

compared with those observed in the subsequent cycles. Thus, the analysis of the eighth cycle (Fig. 2b) indicated a conductivity reduction lower than in the first cycle (i.e. $230 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$) along with slight changes in the pH between 5 and 6. Regarding the ion concentration (Fig. 2d) the patterns seemed to be shifted in such a way that the beginning of the ion removal (from the initial concentrations described in the first cycle) is observed almost after 30 min of the beginning of the charging step when the stack voltage is already at 12 V. At this point, the trends described for the first cycle, i.e. reduction of chloride and sodium level while increasing magnesium contain, were observed again.

The results of this experiment suggest that the CDI system utilizing GF-AC electrodes has the capability to tune mono/divalent cation concentrations by significantly increasing magnesium levels while decreasing sodium concentrations. This process results in a reduction of the Na/Mg concentration ratio from 44 to 7.

Fig. 3. Evolution of ion concentrations during the electroadsorption experiment. A) First cycle and; B) eighth cycle. Evolution of the normalized concentrations ($R_i = C/C_0$) during the first cycle for both, (C) CC and (D) CC–CV experiments. (E) Comparison of $R_{Mg/Na}$ values for both experiments.

3.1.2. Expanding cation adsorption by introducing an intermediate step

To further investigate the extension of the capacitive ion-exchange mechanism, a distinct operational mode for CDI, involving the introduction of a 150-minute intermediate constant-voltage step (CC—CV), was chosen. The main reasons for implementing this modification were as follows: i) to extend the ion removal phase in order to assess the dynamics of mono-divalent ion removal over extended charging durations; an approach that was chosen based on the recognition from earlier studies that charging duration significantly influences mono/divalent ion removal (Guyes et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2012b), ii) to enhance the stability of ion removal performance, as highlighted in a prior study conducted by our team, where intermediate steps were found to be advantageous in this context (García-Quismondo et al., 2016, 2013a), and finally iii) to improve the reproducibility of the ion-balancing phenomenon.

The results of the CC—CV experiment performed at 16 V (Figure. S2) show a consistent conductivity reduction in the range of $520 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, which means an improvement of more than 65 % with respect to the previous experiments. As demonstrated in previous studies, GF-AC electrodes as thick as 6 mm have slow salt adsorption kinetics that might need additional time (provided by the CV step) to achieve its maximum adsorption capacity (Freire et al., 2021). Furthermore, the analysis of the samples by IC confirmed the trends already observed in the first cycle of the previous CC experiment. Thus, reductions of sodium and chloride ions (Fig. 3a) (Na^+ from 286 mg L^{-1} to 167 mg L^{-1} , and Cl^- from 354 mg L^{-1} to 276 mg L^{-1}) were detected along with an increase of magnesium from 7 mg L^{-1} to 23 mg L^{-1} . As displayed in Fig. 3a, sodium concentration reached 131 ppm at the end of the CV after 150 min. In the case of magnesium, after the increase of its concentration during the CC, a linear reduction from the maximum to the initial concentration was observed. Finally, the evolution of the chlorides was different from the sodium, showing a consistent removal from 276 mg L^{-1} to 156 mg L^{-1} that lasted until the end of the CV step. This implies that concentration reductions attained 54 % of sodium and 56 % of chloride while no net reduction of magnesium was achieved during the whole experiment. As a result, at the end of the charging step, SAC and ASAR_c values amounted $4.9 \text{ mg}_{\text{NaCl}} \text{ g}^{-1}$ and $0.021 \text{ mg}_{\text{NaCl}} \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$, respectively. Here it should be highlighted that similar trends were observed when the experiment was performed even at lower stack voltage (14 V) (Figure S3).

As the second part of the analysis, the evolution of the ion concentration during cycling (Fig. 3b) indicated that the shifting of the trends observed in the CC experiment, was mitigated by introducing the CV step. Similar ion-removal ranges were detected for these ions after 150 min of CV (348 mg L^{-1} to 161 mg L^{-1} for Cl^- , and 255 mg L^{-1} to 168 mg L^{-1} for Na^+) pointing out the success of introducing an intermediate step for stabilizing the performance. However, regarding the magnesium, a different pattern from the first cycle was observed showing a consistent removal from 22 mg L^{-1} to 3 mg L^{-1} . This result highlights the change in magnesium behavior between the initial and subsequent cycles, which will be investigated in the following sections.

Finally, separation factors obtained in batch experiments were evaluated. Fig. 3c–3e shows the evolution of the normalized concentrations (R_i) during the first cycle for both, CC (Fig. 3c) and CC—CV (Fig. 3d) experiments. The results clearly show that the concentration of the magnesium in both experiments increased by more than a factor of 3, while the sodium concentration experienced a 50 % reduction. That implies that the monovalent/divalent cation relationship ($R_{\text{Mg}/\text{Na}}$) was incremented by a factor of 6 from the beginning of the experiment, reducing the proportion of Na/Mg from 44 to 7 in the case of the CC experiment and from 38 to 8 in the case of the CC—CV mode Fig. 3e.

Based on the results of both batch experiments, one might consider that the unusual behavior of magnesium ions represents a great opportunity for magnesium capturing and agricultural applications. However, the trends observed in the first cycle were not stable during the cycling process. With the objective of tuning this selectivity and understanding

the mechanism behind the behavior of monovalent and divalent ions, the role of the conditioning process conducted at the beginning of each experiment was further analyzed.

3.2. Critical effect of the electrode surface groups during the conditioning step

In line with Sahray et al.'s model, our hypothesis is that a cation adsorption occurred during the conditioning step, directly influencing the ion concentrations at the onset of the charging phase. This assumption points out the importance of the preliminary step wherein the CDI stack is equilibrated until the feed and outlet conductivity, as well as pH, fall within a similar range. In accordance with that idea, we proposed that sodium and magnesium underwent removal onto the positive electrode. This adsorption process would be primarily driven by ion exchange and electrostatic attraction with the surface functional groups of the activated carbon and the graphite felt (Li et al., 2013).

3.2.1. Elucidating the role of the functional groups

With the aim of identifying the presence of functional groups in the surface of the PICA carbon, XPS experiments were performed (Fig. 4). The analysis revealed that, beside the expected carbon, oxygen was present on the surface of PICA carbon in a C:O atomic ratio of 95:5. Furthermore, the O 1 s region can be fitted with two components centered at 532.4 eV and 530.8 eV, which can be respectively associated with carboxyl (80 %) and hydroxyl (20 %) groups (Idriss, 2021). This correlates with the fitting of the C 1 s region, which requires not only components corresponding to graphite carbon (i.e., asymmetric peak centered at 284.4 eV with shake up features around 291 eV (Biesinger, 2022)), but also components corresponding to sp³ C at 285 eV, C—O at 286.5 eV and C = O at 289 eV for a good fit. In addition to this, it should be considered that previous evaluation of the graphite felts from SGL Carbon by XPS indicated also the presence of oxygen in the surface (O/C: 0.36) being C—O-R (sp³, 6 %) and C = O (sp², 9 %) the most relevant groups in the surface (Eifert et al., 2018).

To evaluate the impact of the surface functionalities on the charge of PICA carbon, zeta potential measurements of the pristine activated carbon were performed, initially using the same electrolyte solution employed in the electrosorption experiments, and subsequently, modifying the pH values between 2 and 10. The results shown in Fig. 5a indicated that the zeta potential for the tested electrolyte was negative (−17 mV). Furthermore, the point of zero charge (pH_{PZC}) of PICA was about 2.45, remaining the negative surface charge over most of the pH range tested (pH above 2.4 - 10.0) which has been previously associated to the deprotonation of surface groups such as hydroxyl and carboxyl. In accordance with that outcome, similar results were obtained for those commercial activated carbons modified by acid treatment (HNO_3) which produced the increase of surface oxygen atoms with a significant contribution of carboxyl groups (Gao et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2016). Finally, XPS and zeta potential results are also in agreement with previous studies performed by TGA that indicated the presence of oxygen groups in the surface of the PICA carbon (Vaquero et al., 2012).

In addition to the physico-chemical properties of the activated carbon, the E_{PZC} was also determined by electrochemical methods (Cyclic Voltammetry). The E_{PZC} refers to the point where the electrode surface holds no excess of ionic charge (Guyes et al., 2021). Fig. 5b shows that the E_{PZC} value for the PICA carbon is 0.17 V. The positive E_{PZC} value indicates the presence of negatively charge groups which is in accordance with XPS analysis and zeta potential measurements. Positive shifting of the E_{PZC} values have been found in the literature as a result of the introduction of negatively charged functional groups carboxyl groups while negative shifting has been observed as a consequence of the addition of positively charged functional groups. With the aim of studying the evolution of E_{PZC} over cycling this parameter was measured again after performing GCD over 100 cycles. The experiment was realized in a three electrodes cell between 0.0 V and 1.0 V, holding the

Fig. 4. Photoelectron spectrum of PICA carbon. A) Survey, B) O 1 s and C) C 1 s region.

Fig. 5. A) Zeta potential measurements of activated carbon performed between pH 2 and 10 in an electrolyte solution similar to the one employed in the CDI experiments, i.e. Na^+ from 221 mg L^{-1} , $20 \text{ mg L}^{-1} \text{ Mg}^{2+}$, and Cl^- from 402 mg L^{-1} . B) Determination of E_{PZC} by CV. The graph shows the cyclic voltammetry of the pristine electrode (CV₁) along with the one of the electrode after being cycled galvanostatically for 100 cycles (CV₁₀₀). As a result of the oxidation process, a shift in the E_{PZC} value was observed.

voltage at 1.0 V for 30 min. As a result of this process, that simulates the anode oxidation in the CDI cell during operation, the E_{PZC} , as expected, was shifted to more positive values ($E_{\text{PZC}} = 0.47$) which points out to the increase of surface functionalities due to the carbon oxidation reaction.

Ion adsorption is strongly influenced by the E_{PZC} in such a way that, for electrode potentials above the E_{PZC} , anion adsorption is expected whereas potential values below E_{PZC} will lead to cation adsorption. In the case of the anode (positive electrode), following the model of Sahray

et al., for a conditioning process in which the discharge voltage is smaller than the E_{PZC} of the anode, a significant amount of cations will be adsorbed in the anode. Once the charging phase begins and the anode potential exceeds the anode E_{PZC} , the cations are desorbed and the anions starts getting adsorbed. These findings, and the first-cycle CDI results, made us hypothesizing that the sodium and magnesium adsorption process might occur through interaction with SOGs such as carboxyl and hydroxyl functionalities as they have capacity to exchange cations. As

stated by Rivera-Utrilla et al., the acidic oxygen groups might behave as ion-exchange centers exchanging metallic ions, while releasing protons at $\text{pH} > \text{pH}_{\text{PZC}}$ (Rivera-Utrilla et al., 2011). As described by Wu et al., in the absence of electronic charge, the surface charge developed by the ionized SOGs is compensated by the charge of the ions in the electrolyte (Wu et al., 2022). In our case, due to their smaller hydrated radius and hydration energy, sodium ions are expected to adsorb faster than magnesium ions (Valiskó et al., 2007).

It is important to note here that, independently of the initial number of SOGs in the electrodes, their density is likely to increase during the CDI cycling process, particularly in the positive electrode (anode), due to a well-known oxidation process (Bayram and Ayranci, 2011; Chen et al., 2013; Cohen et al., 2013; Gao et al., 2014; He et al., 2016; Lado et al., 2015; Changyong Zhang et al., 2018). Anodic polarization leads to the direct oxidation of the positive carbon electrodes, although indirect oxidation may also contribute, as a consequence of the hydroxyl radical generation (this latter process could also affect the negative electrode) (Bayram and Ayranci, 2011). This mechanism, as highlighted by Sahray et al., will lead to further improve the monovalent cation selectivity (Sahray et al., 2023).

The oxidation of the GF-AC upon cycling was previously demonstrated in a study from our group, wherein the modification of the electrode potentials during performance was analyzed using a reference electrode (Wang et al., 2020). The potential profile of the positive electrode exhibited deviations from linearity, suggesting the occurrence of faradaic reactions, mainly carbon oxidation. Moreover, research aimed at investigating the effects of electrochemical ageing (potential

application of 1.2 V vs. RHE to the GF using an acidic electrolyte) on the GF materials determined that this process led to a significant increase of the O/C ratio from 0.36 to 0.46 and the relative content of C = O groups from 9 to 13 % (Eifert et al., 2018). In addition to this, Chen et al. performed Boehm titration studies of activated carbon electrodes submitted to a CDI aging test, revealing an important increase in the number of functional groups such as $-\text{COOH}$ (0.027 to 0.391 mmol g^{-1}) and $-\text{COOR}$ (0.006 to 0.197 mmol g^{-1}) (Chen et al., 2013). Finally, Zhang et al. corroborated that finding when pristine and aged three-dimensional (3D) graphene/carbon nanotubes (G-CNTs) hybrid electrodes were analyzed by XPS. Results indicated an increase of the oxygen's content on the electrode surface with the continuous charging-discharging cycles detecting an increase of different functional groups, such as hydroxyls, ketones and carboxyl moieties. (Helan Zhang et al., 2018). To support this, additional E_{PZC} measurements were performed using PICA carbon electrodes (dip coating of carbon paper) submitted to a cycle galvanostatic charge-discharge experiment over 100 cycles (Fig. 7b) The results indicate that upon cycling the E_{PZC} of the working electrodes (anodes) became even more negative.

3.2.2. Proposed mechanism

Considering all these findings, a mechanism for the interaction between cations and GF-AC is proposed in Fig. 6. Initially, the ions are adsorbed in the conditioning step due to the interaction between the SOGs and the ions (Fig. 6a). Due to the negative electrode charge at the anode (positive electrode) induce by the SOG, a significant amount of cations will be adsorbed. Once the electrodes are polarized and before

Fig. 6. Schematics of the proposed mono-divalent mechanism showing the different interactions between the ions and the electrodes during the capacitive deionization experiment. A) Open circuit voltage conditioning process; B) Polarization: ion exchange phase; C) Polarization: ion swapping; D) Ion desorption step (discharge); E) Identification of the 4 different phases of the mechanism using a CC-CV batch experiment previously described in Fig. 3a as an example.

the anode potential becomes higher than the E_{pZC} , sodium and magnesium ions are electrostatically desorbed from the positive electrode into the solution, a phenomenon previously described as the co-ion expulsion effect (Wu et al., 2016) (Fig. 6b). Thus, as result of the co-ions being expelled from the electrodes due to their similar charge, an increase in conductivity in the effluent is observed (called “inversion peak”). At this point, it is expected that the desorption of magnesium will be hindered due to the strong electrostatic forces between divalent cations and the SOGs, whereas sodium ions will be rapidly released from the positively charged electrode. This effect will be more evident due to the larger thickness of the graphite felt (4.6 mm) electrodes employed in this work compared to activated carbon electrodes (0.6 - 0.2 mm) typically used in the CDI literature. Simultaneously, due to its smaller hydrated radius, lower hydration enthalpy, faster diffusion rate and higher concentration, sodium ions will be adsorbed faster onto the negatively polarized electrode than magnesium ions (Gamaethiralalage et al., 2021). As a result, our experiments indicate no or hardly any sodium adsorption during the early stages of polarization, followed by a rapid electro-sorption (Fig. 6b). Besides that, the slow desorption of previously adsorbed magnesium promoted by the thick GF electrodes, in combination with its sluggish electrosorption onto the negatively charged electrode resulted in the increment of the magnesium concentration within the electrolyte solution. This observation is further supported by the studies of Valisjko et al. (Valiskó et al., 2007), indicating that as the surface charge intensifies due to polarization, a layer with a larger amount of small ions (Na^+ , in our case) is favored over large divalent ions due to the prevalence of entropic effect over the electrostatic forces.

Once the magnesium desorption process concludes, the batch experiments revealed a decrease in magnesium concentration, which can likely be attributed to adsorption on the negative electrode (Fig. 6c). Here, we observe the possibility of a phenomenon known as time-dependent ion-selectivity. Time-dependent selectivity was observed by Zhao et al., when charging carbon porous electrodes in multicomponent electrolytes (Na^+ and Ca^{2+}) (Zhao et al., 2012b). It was reported that, initially, the majority of monovalent cations were preferentially adsorbed in the EDLs, followed by a gradual replacement by the minority of divalent cations. This phenomenon was explained by theoretical modelling based on non-linear theory for transport and capacitive charging in multi-ionic solutions. Using microporous carbon materials, further studies developed by Suss's group (Guyes et al., 2021; Uwayid et al., 2022) revealed an ion swapping mechanism. It was observed that during short charging periods monovalent ion removal was favored, while longer charging times led to the preferential adsorption of divalent ions. This outcome is attributed to the increased electrostatic force acting on divalent ions in the EDLs. This conclusion on the preference for monovalent selectivity was also more recently supported by other researchers (Choi et al., 2016; Guyes et al., 2021; Seo et al., 2010).

Finally, at the end of the charging phase, the discharging step will take place resulting in the ion desorption from the electrodes back into the electrolyte solution (Fig. 6d). In this context, the proposed mechanism elucidates how the interaction between the SOGs and the cations during the conditioning step strongly influence the composition of the effluent produced by the CDI reactor (Fig. 6e). Nevertheless, as the cycling process advances, the effect of the conditioning process might mitigate, following sodium and magnesium the expected removal trends. Conversely, additional experiments have demonstrated that, once an experiment concludes and a new one is initiated using the aforementioned conditioning process, magnesium desorption is observed again as soon as the electrodes are polarized. Therefore, the incorporation of a conditioning process in the CDI operation protocol is expected to ensure consistent performance.

To conclude the analysis, one should consider that the progressive oxidation throughout the cycling progress will result in to the increase of SOGs, as indirectly demonstrated by the E_{pZC} shift to more positive values. This modification will further enhance cation adsorption during the following conditioning phase of the subsequent experiments. Hence,

our observations underscore that this process recurs with each new experiment, highlighting the consistency of this phenomenon.

3.3. Computational modelling analysis

To support the hypothesis described in the previous section about the adsorption/desorption dynamics of the mono and divalent cations and evaluate the effect of different surface groups that might be present in the GF-AC, a computational modelling analysis was performed. The results of the free energies (Figure S4) indicate the higher affinity of cations for the electrode when deprotonated groups are present in the electrode surface, as expected. Moreover, a higher affinity was observed for magnesium over sodium ions, especially in the presence of SOGs such as catechol, ketone and hydroxyl groups. It is also expected that the stronger affinity of magnesium over sodium ions will impact on the following phase, slowing the magnesium desorption from the positive electrode once the electrodes are polarized.

With the aim of completing the analysis, the free energies of the process in which sodium ions are replaced by magnesium cations in the EDL were calculated using the following reaction scheme:

And applying the following formula to calculate the replacement free energy (RFE):

$$\text{RFE} = G[\text{GO}-\text{Mg}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4] + G[\text{Na}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6] - G[\text{Mg}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6] - G[\text{GO}-\text{Na}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$$

where G stands for the calculated Gibbs free energy. In other words, $\text{RFE} < 0$ indicates a thermodynamically favorable replacement of sodium by magnesium cations on the graphene-oxide. In order to take into account the tenfold higher concentrations of sodium cations with respect to the magnesium, a correction factor of $RT\ln[10] \approx 5.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ is added to the free energies of replacement.

The results presented in Fig. 7 point out that the calculations predict the similar trends, independent on the functional and basis set. Analysis of the results shows that when the surface-oxygen groups are carrying a negative charge (after polarization of the electrode), there is a clear preference for adsorption of magnesium over sodium ions. The DFT results are in qualitative agreement with the experiments in which, after longer times of polarization magnesium ions are still being adsorbed while sodium ions are desorbed. When translated to CDI, such behavior indicates that the replacement of sodium by magnesium ions would take

Fig. 7. Computed free energies (in kJ mol^{-1}) of replacement of Na^+ by Mg^{2+} on a graphene-oxide model with various oxygen-groups. The subscript (m) stands for oxygen-groups located at the ring of the ovale molecule. All other groups are at the edges.

place in the EDL.

3.4. Single-pass (SP) experiments

To assess the potential application of CDI for scenarios requiring a modification in the mono/divalent composition of a solution, such as reducing the SAR index in agricultural operations, we examined the operation of the CDI system in a single-pass mode. In this setup, rather than recirculating the electrolyte, 220 L of fresh electrolyte solution ($\sigma = 1248 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, $\text{pH} = 5.59$) were pumped at 40 L h^{-1} through the CDI stack collecting the treated solution in a secondary tank.

The results from the experiments performed at 14 V and 16 V (6.3 A m^{-2} , as charging current density), where samples of 5 L and 10 L were collected and subsequently analyzed by IC, confirmed the cation adsorption/desorption dynamics observed in the batch experiments also apply in the SP configuration (Fig. 8a, data collected in Table S3). SP experiments allowed to clearly differentiate the stages previously described in Fig. 6 and validated by the DFT calculations. First, there is the conditioning process (Phase A), followed by magnesium desorption along with the initial brief sodium desorption (10–15 min), succeeded by a strong adsorption of chloride and sodium (Phase B). Consequently, significant removal of chloride (14 V: 440 to 400 mg L^{-1} ; 16 V: 443 to 379 mg L^{-1} , at the lowest point) and sodium (14 V: 314 to 176 mg L^{-1} ; 16 V: 291 to 188 mg L^{-1} at the lowest point) was detected while magnesium suffered a continuous desorption process (14 V: 22 to 29 mg L^{-1} ; 16 V: 22 to 32 mg L^{-1} at the highest point) lasting 150 min. In the third stage (Phase C), magnesium was no longer desorbed and started to decrease (16 V, down from 22 to 15 mg L^{-1}), while the sodium concentration in the effluent began to increase, suggesting that an exchange within the EDL was taking place.

$R_{\text{Mg}/\text{Na}}$ values were also analyzed for both experiments. Fig. 8b shows that the proportion of magnesium/sodium in the effluent increased up to 100 % in both cases reaching maximum $R_{\text{Mg}/\text{Na}}$ values between 2.0–2.3. Moreover, $R_{\text{Mg}/\text{Na}}$ values above 1 were consistently obtained during the experiments over more than 230 min demonstrating the capability of CDI to deliver an effluent in which magnesium concentration was substantially increased with respect to sodium. This outcome is highly relevant because it proves that the CDI system is able to produce an effluent with a higher divalent cation proportion than in the inlet solution achieving significantly higher production rates ($8.0\text{--}8.1 \text{ L m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$) than in batch mode ($0.5\text{--}0.8 \text{ L m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$). Conversely, it is also fair to recognize that batch mode enables to reach significantly higher $R_{\text{Mg}/\text{Na}}$ values (5–6) than single-pass operation (2).

The single-pass configuration of the CDI system not only facilitated a more comprehensive evaluation of the mono/divalent cation proportion but also enabled us to calculate operational parameters of the CDI system. In this sense, the salt electrosorption achieved in these experiments, considering the removal of major components (sodium and chloride),

was 17 g , that means SAC values of $8.9\text{--}9.0 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$, and ASAR_C of $0.025 \text{ mg g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. Furthermore, water production reached $8 \text{ L h}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and energy consumption associated to that performance values ranged $0.34\text{--}0.45 \text{ kWh m}^{-3}$ and $0.27\text{--}0.35 \text{ kWh mol}^{-1}$ when normalized by amount of NaCl removed (results are summarized in Table S3).

3.5. Impact of electrolyte concentration and composition

With the aim of evaluating the effect of the ionic feed concentrations of the electrolyte in the mono-divalent behavior, experiments were performed increasing the concentrations of the different ions significantly (Na^+ $466\text{--}679 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, Cl^- $880\text{--}1200 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, Mg^{2+} $43\text{--}56 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$). Current densities (10.4 A m^{-2} and 20.8 A m^{-2}) and stack voltages (11 V and 14 V) were adapted to the higher conductivity of the electrolyte.

As displayed in Fig. 9a–c, the results of the SP experiments indicate that, despite the increase in ion concentrations and the modification of operational conditions, the behavior of magnesium and sodium ions remains similar to what was previously observed at lower concentrations. That indicates that the magnesium desorption was clearly appreciated in all the experiments, resulting in the production of an effluent with $R_{\text{Mg}/\text{Na}}$ higher than 1 for more than 100 min Fig. 9d. Additionally, Fig. 9a and Fig. 9c also show how the decrease of the current density led to slower kinetics in terms of sodium adsorption and magnesium desorption, which can be clearly appreciated at the beginning of the experiment. These results are in agreement with Zhao et al., pointing out the need to fine-tune current densities and flow in single-pass CDI operation to maximize ion separation being high current densities particularly advantageous when looking for a fast response (Zhao et al., 2012a).

Performance values of these experiments were collected in Table S3 showing that the increase of ion concentration led to higher SAC values ($11.1\text{--}15.4 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$), faster adsorption kinetics ($0.067\text{--}0.083 \text{ mg min}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$) and similar production levels in the range of $7\text{--}9 \text{ L h}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$. Higher removal capacities have been previously observed when increasing the electrolyte concentration (Lado et al., 2015). The main reason behind this behavior is the reduction of the double layer thickness producing the enlargement of the electrode capacitance due to the larger contribution of micropores (Yang et al., 2001). Moreover, the larger concentration of ions in the solution reduces the resistance in the electrolyte affecting to parameters such as the charge efficiency and energy consumption. Thus, higher charge efficiencies (27 %) and lower specific molar energy consumptions ($0.15\text{--}0.17$ vs $0.27 \text{ kWh mol}^{-1}$) were obtained for similar stack voltages (14 V) when increasing the concentration of the electrolyte (Table S3).

Further experiments performed at significantly higher concentrations (Na^+ : $2715\text{--}3220 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, Cl^- : $5774\text{--}7880 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, Mg^{2+} : $277\text{--}690 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) confirmed previous results. First, the previously

Fig. 8. A) Evolution of ion concentrations in the single pass experiments performed at 14 V. B) $R_{\text{Mg}/\text{Na}}$ values for both experiments performed at 14 V and 16 V.

Fig. 9. Evolution of ion concentrations in single-pass experiments performed in a CC–CV mode using fresh electrolyte solution (conductivity $\approx 2880 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, pH = 7.3) constantly pumped at 40 L h^{-1} through the CDI stack. Experiments were performed at 20.8 A m^{-2} , (A) 14 V and (B) 11 V. C) Additional experiments were performed at 14 V and lower current density (10.4 A m^{-2}) using a slightly higher conductivity. D) Time-dependent values of $R_{\text{Mg}/\text{Na}}$ for all the experiments area also displayed.

observed mono/divalent behavior persisted even after a tenfold increase in ion concentration regarding the initial experiments (Figure S5). Second, the increment of the initial concentration of the solution leads to the acceleration of the magnesium desorption process (25 min vs. 100 min in the previous case). In fact, to detect the rapid modification of the ion concentrations the sampling protocol was adapted as explained in the Supplementary Info section (Figure S6).

Additionally, it was decided to validate the results when calcium was used as a divalent cation instead of magnesium. Following this idea, experiments using an electrolyte with the following characteristics (Na^+ : $457\text{--}585 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, Cl^- : $1995\text{--}1998 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, Ca^{2+} : $225\text{--}253 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$,

conductivity: $5630 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, pH: 6.4) were performed using 10.4 A m^{-2} and 20.8 A m^{-2} as current densities and 14 V as maximum stack voltage. The results of the experiments displayed in Fig. 10 and Figure S7 show the same patterns described for the experiments performed using magnesium as divalent cation. Thus, a significant removal of chloride (1998 to 1713 mg L^{-1} at the lowest point) and sodium (457 to 365 mg L^{-1}) was observed while calcium suffered a desorption process (253 to 267 mg L^{-1} at the highest point) that lasted around 60 min. After that point the concentration of calcium decreased to 208 mg L^{-1} . Interestingly, similar to magnesium, calcium also showed an accelerated rate of removal as the sodium concentration in the effluent

Fig. 10. A) Evolution of ion concentrations in the experiment performed using calcium instead of magnesium as divalent cation. Maximum stack voltage and current density were set at 14 V and 20.8 A m^{-2} , respectively. B) R_i values for the different ions along with $R_{\text{Ca}/\text{Na}}$ were also evaluated.

began to increase. This observation indicates a potential substitution occurring in the EDL.

Finally, it is noteworthy that as a consequence of the mono/divalent dynamics, an effluent with an $R_{Ca/Na}$ higher than 1 was produced for 90 min, reaching its maximum point at 1.28 after 40 min. These results confirm that the behavior observed during CDI operation is consistent for both divalent cations, Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , thereby validating the potential future application of CDI to increase SAR and reduce conductivity, improving the water quality for irrigation. The decrease in the separation factor from 2.30 (Fig. 8B) to 1.28 (Fig. 9D) appears to be linked to the modification of the electrolyte composition, particularly the balance between the concentrations of monovalent and divalent cations. Consequently, larger separation factors were obtained when electrolytes with higher ratios between divalent and monovalent cations were tested. Thus, $R_{Mg/Na}$ of 2.3 was obtained for water compositions of Na^+ : 291–314 $mg L^{-1}$, Cl^- : 440–443 $mg L^{-1}$, Mg^{2+} : 22 $mg L^{-1}$ in which the relationship between Mg:Na was $\approx 1:14$ (Fig. 8B). In the case of water compositions with a bit lower Mg:Na ratio (Mg:Na $\approx 1:11$ –12, Na^+ 466–679 $mg L^{-1}$, Cl^- 880–1200 $mg L^{-1}$, Mg^{2+} 43–56 $mg L^{-1}$) $R_{Mg/Na}$ values below 2 were obtained (Fig. 9C). Finally, for those experiments performed with Ca^{2+} instead Mg^{2+} , the Ca:Na relationship was reduced to 2.0–2.3, (Na^+ : 457–585 $mg L^{-1}$, Cl^- : 1995–1998 $mg L^{-1}$, Ca^{2+} : 225–253 $mg L^{-1}$), which leads to a significant reduction of a $R_{Ca/Na}$ values of 1.28. Furthermore, the increase of the electrolyte concentration is the other factor that affects the separation factor as it can be observed in Figure S5A (Na^+ : 3220 $mg L^{-1}$, Cl^- : 5774 $mg L^{-1}$, Mg^{2+} : 277 $mg L^{-1}$) in which despite having a Mg:Na ratio of 11.62, the separation factor was reduced to $R_{Mg/Na}$: 1.04. The composition of the electrolyte significantly influences the dynamics of the capacitive ion exchange mechanisms by factors such as the formation of the EDL and the potential of zero charge. Further evaluation of this aspect is necessary to determine the extent of its application.

3.6. Validation of the hypothesis in a 9-Cell cdi stack lab-scale reactor

Once the hypothesis about the mono/divalent ion behavior was confirmed using higher feed concentrations and compositions (Ca^{2+} instead of Mg^{2+}), an additional validation of our hypothesis was carried out using a different CDI stack. In this case, a 9-Cell CDI Stack equipped the same kind of GF-AC electrodes (300 cm^2) described in previous studies from our group (Lado et al., 2021a, 2021b; Wang et al., 2020) was used to verify the reproducibility of the results found in the CDI pilot plant. Due to the cycling process experienced by the lab stack in those studies (more than 350 galvanostatic cycles, as described in (Lado et al., 2021a)), it is expected that the positive electrodes of the lab stack should

have already suffered certain degree of oxidation. Therefore, these additional experiments aimed to, firstly, validate the results in a different CDI stack, and secondly, demonstrate that the behavior of mono/divalent ions remained similar to that observed in the larger CDI plant, even after an extended cycling process

With the objective of testing these hypotheses, three consecutive batch experiments were performed using an electrolyte with the following composition; 168–179 $mg L^{-1} Na^+$, 28–32 $mg L^{-1} Mg^{2+}$ and 381–391 $mg L^{-1} Cl^-$. The results of the experiments shown in Fig. 11A (2nd exp.) and Figure S8A-C (1st and 3rd exp.) clearly verified the reproducibility of the patterns observed in the previous experiments and the robustness of the results. Moreover, analysis of the $R_{Mg/Na}$ indicates that the CDI system was able to produce consistently an effluent with values between 1.6–1.9 (Fig. 11B and Figure S8C). This is an additional proof of the reproducibility of the performance when using the 3D GF electrodes not just using the same CDI system but also in two stacks of different scales and after different cycling processes.

4. Conclusions

The capacitive ion-exchange mechanism provided by functionalized electrodes is supported by the experimental evidence obtained from our study, utilizing a CDI pilot plant and spiked real water samples. This mechanism facilitates the removal of monovalent ions from water while augmenting the concentration of divalent cations in the solution. This behavior is achieved by using electrodes with a high presence of SOG that allows to capture a significant amount of cations during the conditioning process. Once the charging step begins, the slower desorption kinetics of divalent cations previously adsorbed at the anode along with the simultaneous fast capture of monovalent ions on the cathode lead to the reduction of the SAR of the electrolyte.

The effectiveness of the capacitive ion-exchange mechanism was validated through numerous practical experiments in which sodium and magnesium concentrations were modified, affirming the applicability of the proposed model even at high ion concentrations. Moreover, the use of different operational (CC and CC–CV) and flow (batch and single pass) modes were employed to optimize the separation factors attending to other practical aspects such as the water production and the energy consumption. Thus, batch experiments demonstrated higher $R_{Mg/Na}$ values (5–6) compared to single-pass operation (2) yet the latter expanded water production significantly from 0.5 to 0.8 $L m^{-2} h^{-1}$ in batch to 8.0–8.1 $L m^{-2} h^{-1}$. Furthermore, our results also confirmed that the conclusions drawn for magnesium were also valid for calcium ions, showcasing the efficacy of the proposed CDI stack in manipulating the concentrations of these ions in treated water. Finally, the robustness

Fig. 11. Batch experiments performed with 9-Cell CDI Stack using CC–CV mode. A current density of $6.7 A m^{-2}$ (charge and discharge) and a voltage limit for the stack of 9.9 V (1.1 V per cell) were established. A constant voltage step of 1 h was set after charging at 9.9 V and discharging at 0 V. A volume of 4.4 L of electrolyte containing 168–179 $mg L^{-1} Na^+$, 28–32 $mg L^{-1} Mg^{2+}$ and 381–391 $mg L^{-1} Cl^-$ was flushed at $15.6 L h^{-1}$ through the CDI stack. A) Results of the second of the three consecutive experiments showing an exceptional reproducibility of the trends already described in former experiments performed with the pilot plant CDI system. Additional two experiments are shown in Figure S8. B) $R_{Mg/Na}$ values show the good correlation among the test performed with the lab CDI stack.

and reliability of the capacitive ion-exchange mechanism was further affirmed by a CDI laboratory 9-cell stack that cycled for over 350 cycles, consistently exhibiting the anticipated behavior. This proof substantiates the adaptability and scalability of the proposed methods across various equipment sizes.

This research significantly expands and validates Sahray et al.'s theoretical model through practical pilot plant experimentation, specifically in agricultural applications that demand the reduction of ionic conductivity and an increase in the SAR index. Thus, this study suggests that employing an energy-efficient CDI treatment in irrigation systems holds promise for reducing the SAR index in water, effectively mitigating soil sodification risks. This approach shows potential for enhancing agricultural productivity by maintaining suitable water quality for irrigation, thereby supporting sustainable crop production.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Julio J. Lado: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Enrique García-Quismondo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Alba Fombona-Pascual:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Andreas Mavrandonakis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Carlos de la Cruz:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Freddy E. Oropeza:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Victor A. de la Peña O'Shea:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Louis C.P.M. de Smet:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jesús Palma:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.watres.2024.121469](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2024.121469).

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